

Priorities for Research and Innovation for Copernicus

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List of Acronyms

ACIX	Atmospheric Correction Intercomparison Exercise
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CCTH	Copernicus Coastal Thematic Hub
CDS	Climate Data Store
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CHIME	Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment
CIS ECOSTAT WG	Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive Working Group
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CTH	Copernicus Thematic Hubs
CWTH	Copernicus Water Thematic Hub
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
DPSIR	Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response framework
EE12 GALENE	Earth Explorer 12 - Global Assessment of Limnological, Estuarine and Neritic Ecosystems
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Earth Observation (satellite, aerial, in situ)
EO4SDG	Earth Observation for the Sustainable Development Goals
EOMORES	Horizon 2020: Earth Observation based services for Monitoring and Reporting of Ecological Status
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurement

GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOGLOWS	GEO Global Water Sustainability
GLEON	Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network
GLIMR	Geosynchronous Littoral Imaging and Monitoring Radiometer (EVI-5) (GLIMR)
GRACE	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment
HR-OC	Copernicus Marine High-Resolution Ocean Colour Service
HYPERNETS	Horizon 2020 project “A new hyperspectral radiometer integrated in automated networks of water and land bidirectional reflectance measurements for satellite validation”
IRL	Implementation Readiness Level
MONOCLE	Horizon 2020 project “Multiscale Observation Networks for Optical monitoring of Coastal waters, Lakes and Estuaries”
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC)
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NMHS	National Meteorological and Hydrological Services
OOPC	Ocean Observations Physics and Climate Panel
PACE	Plankton, Aerosol, Cloud, ocean Ecosystem
R&D	Research and Development
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
SBG	Surface Biology and Geology
Sen-ET	Sentinels for Evapotranspiration
SWOT	Surface Water and Ocean Topography
TIR	Thermal Infrared Sensor
TOPC	Terrestrial Observation Panel for Climate
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAV	Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle
WFD	Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)
WG	Working Group
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation

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1. Executive Summary

The desired impacts of the Copernicus Services are to support and develop key policies, monitor their implementation (e.g., to ensure healthy and productive aquatic environments), and deliver actionable information to help the global community attain the Sustainable Development Goals. At the same time, the Services are expected to support downstream business and the European economy through brokerage of additional services, through efficiency gains (e.g., in the water utilities sector), or both. In order to achieve this, processes of user consultation and service evolution are built into the Copernicus Services concept.

As requirements and expectations, as well as space assets evolve, the Copernicus Services have in some areas expanded to a point where transparency and consistency in the product portfolio are no longer in step with technical improvements. The present services can be seen as the result of a continuous technology push, despite efforts to guide development from end-user consultation. This has led to some obvious and some less obvious gaps in product development, requiring further Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) activities to resolve. Meanwhile, product development and validation have not progressed at the same pace as space assets have, resulting in suboptimal uncertainty characterization and lower uptake of products than desired.

Proposed measures to better serve a wide range of user needs include continued development of space assets to meet user needs, and introducing new products, particularly those in high demand in the modelling community seeking to enhance forecasting abilities and climate resilience. More recently, emerging technologies to boost in situ data collection efforts at relatively low cost (uncrewed aerial observation, citizen science, automation) have seen significant development and demonstration activity, which should be introduced more widely to support the services.

This report contains an overview of the recommendations for improvement to the Copernicus water services landscape, collected over two years through thematic workshops, analysis of the needs of a range of sectors and policy, and expert consultation.

Through this overview, we can corroborate the most pressing challenge areas and recommend immediate and long-term actions for improvement. Whilst this report focuses on analysing Research and Innovation activities, several coordinating and capacity building actions are closely linked and therefore included as well.

Top level findings of this work are as follows:

- Thematic data collections should be created to support a wider use base. These platforms can serve to introduce a wider range of data sources than those originating from the Services, and for capacity building and advanced data analytics. It is recognised that thematic data collections require a degree of harmonization of data and the user experience, which is not presently available.
- The future success of the Copernicus water-related Services is closely tied to its ability to work with and shape in situ data networks, to arrive at an integrated water monitoring solution, deliver products with uncertainty characterisation, and support the introduction of ('higher-level') biogeochemical products and the full set of Essential Climate Variables. Near-real time data sharing mechanisms and incentives to in situ data producers are, however, largely lacking.
- New and existing space assets, including those from non-European missions, should be combined to produce the highest possible spatiotemporal products across the land-sea continuum. At the same time, observation challenges in the nearshore area need to be tackled through strategic in situ data collection, improved atmospheric correction procedures, and data analytics. The resulting product selection should provide actionable information to a wide range of sectors including food, drinking water, transport, and assurance.

2. Introduction

2.1. Problem definition

The Water-ForCE project was designed to address several key challenges facing the current organisation and content of the Copernicus Services. The challenges below follow those that were *a priori* set out with additions following from the fact-finding phase of the project. Ultimately, the way in which these challenges are likely to be addressed in different scenarios for 'water' products in Copernicus is laid out in a Roadmap, another output from this project.

To link RDI priorities to the key challenges, it is useful to restate them as desired impacts, challenges to achieve these, and solution areas in which progress must be made:

Impacts:

- Copernicus Services supporting **development of key policy areas** (Water Framework Directive, Bathing Water Directive, Flood Risk Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive) and related international initiatives (e.g., integrated drought management).
- Copernicus Services supporting the **monitoring** of the implementation of these policies in related fields (agriculture, transport, food security, energy, the European Green Deal, integrated drought management).
- Copernicus Services supporting the **Sustainable Development Goals** (especially No. 6 Clean Water and Sanitation and 2 Zero Hunger).

Challenges:

- **Fragmentation** in data and products, such that the needs of data brokers and end-users across sectors are not fully met.
- Limited (**trust in**) **product quality** of inland water variables.
- **Lack of integration** of products and services to achieve a coherent and consistent inland water monitoring system.

- Lack of capacity with key stakeholders across policy and management sectors to use and co-develop products and services.

Solution areas:

- Strengthening the portfolio of services and products through current and future space assets.
- Developing new and upscaling prototype products, including high-level biogeochemical products.
- Developing mixed observation / modelling approaches to deliver key variables with hindcast and forecast features.
- Develop change detection approaches for water availability, water quality, water storage, water fluxes, temperature, lake and river ice and coastal areas.
- Achieving spatiotemporal consistency in products from lakes and rivers and the transition from land to ocean through harmonization of methods and validation activities.
- Developing innovative methodologies to characterise uncertainties, including in situ data collection and crowdsourcing.
- Capacity building (digital skills).
- Intuitive and FAIR data and product catalogues.

Throughout the Water-ForCE project, expert communities have analysed gaps and requirements for the future of the Copernicus water-related services, largely within disciplinary bounds such as remote observation of water quality, water quantity, and modelling and in situ observation. These recommendations have now been analysed, grouped and prioritised in an attempt to identify short, medium and long-term actions to improve and expand the services, cutting across science, management and industrial disciplines.

This document primarily analyses recommendations for Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) made by the consulted communities of experts and industry representatives, as well as by the experts included in the Water-ForCE consortium. It is

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useful to compare where these groups confirmed gaps and challenges, as well as where potential strengths and solutions have been suggested.

It is important to note that this is a deductive analysis, with themes derived from the set of recommendations contributed earlier in the project. Therefore, this approach reflects the composition and opinion of the consulted expert groups. Detailed analysis is provided through the specific reports stemming from individual Water-ForCE work packages, all of which are available through the project website and referenced herein.

2.2. Related work

Water-ForCE is in the process of developing a roadmap for the Copernicus water-related services, in which several scenarios for improvement are considered. The recommendations highlighted in this report, as well as those highlighted in reports D6.1 (focussed on Capacity Building), and D6.3 (downstream business opportunities), are part of the process to inform this roadmap, and in particular to assess the state of maturity of directions for change included in the roadmap. In addition, the roadmap covers several aspects which are not yet explored here, including an identification of the parties (stakeholders) involved in implementing the future scenarios, the timeframe for implementation of key measures, and overall feasibility.

2.3. Classification

Throughout this document, recommendations are classified into four categories of action. Because many recommendations require multiple types of action, this is only a first order grouping and similar actions may be found under separate themes. The classification is shown in Figure 1 and includes focus on Coordination, Research and Development, Innovation, and Trust and Confidence enhancing actions.

Figure 1 Primary classification of the recommendations

The focus of the current document is on Research and Development and Innovation categories. A comprehensive list of the recommendations resulting from expert analysis during the first two years of the Water-ForCE project is provided in the Appendix.

Initial efforts have been made to separate priority actions from the full set of recommendations. A priority action is defined here as an action which tackles (1) an urgent issue, or (2) a blocking issue which requires resolving before other improvements can be made, or (3) an improvement for which technological or implementation maturity is already high such that the cost / benefit ratio is high.

This document further classifies (priority) actions by application domain or a specific impact. Examples of impacts are increased trust in satellite-derived products by describing product uncertainties or by improved uptake in near-shore waters, the use of future space assets which better connect observation capabilities to the needs of the modelling community, or harmonised use of data from a wider range of platforms and associated observation scales (such as citizen science, drones, and satellite sensors). Management themes include mitigation of hazards, food and water security, transport and recreation, or climate

adaptation and mitigation. As with all classifications used, the recommended actions are often relevant to more than one theme.

A number of recommendations raised by the expert communities consulted in Water-ForCE transcend all themes and application domains and are required to ensure that the Copernicus services deliver for policy and industry in Europe and beyond. These requirements can be interpreted as a set of tests for the successful evolution of the Services for water and they form the foundation of the Roadmap. They are included in the next section to provide context to the Research and Innovation themed recommended actions.

3. Thematic priority actions

Coordination

Research

Innovation

Trust

3.1. [G] General recommendations for Copernicus water-related services and thematic hub development

The recommendations in this section resulted from multiple expert and user interviews, workshop activities and disciplinary gap analysis. Whilst this set of recommendations does not sit within a specific thematic area, they describe how the water-related Copernicus services should evolve to expand their scope, serve a wider user base throughout research, industry and management, achieve a wider global reach, and see increased societal impact whilst supporting policy. The majority of recommendations stem from interactions in Water-ForCE WP1 and the associated reports, with any other sources indicated below. As these are generic requirements for the water-related services rather than specific Research and Innovation actions, they are provided for context and not analysed in detail.

G1: Connecting policy, industry, and research requirements

- Expand user requirements analysis to more representatives of the private water management sector, and from the mining and industry sectors (note: these sectors were also underrepresented in Water-ForCE consultations)
- Gain a better understanding of the requirements of a water-smart society and the Water-Oriented Living Labs (identified in 24 European countries).

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- Coordinate requirements for in situ information coming from the EEA and from water managers in the public and private sectors. This broadly includes activities on lakes, river level monitoring, inflow to coastal zones, and the use of citizen science data for calibration/validation of satellite EO water quality products.

G2: Sector development and partnerships for a water-smart society

- Emphasise the role of Earth observation service providers in the expansion of the market for water information and in thematic data hubs or platforms tailored to the inland water sector.
- Focus the development of new services for the water market on multi-source information and the use of smart technologies.
- Emphasise multi-source analytics to meet the user demand for situational awareness in water management.
- Provide user-friendly data platforms that enable rapid development of ML pipelines for EO data, with support in the form of example code and video tutorials (D5.3)

G3: Vastly improve awareness, training and international outreach

- Raise awareness, through the services, on how products can be found and used in the DIASes and the new Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (see also report D3.2).
- Improve awareness with private companies in the (non-EO) water sector and those responsible for water monitoring, regarding the capabilities of EO and Copernicus.
- Support creation of a dedicated thematic Water Hub which seamlessly collates data and information from a wide range of sources: satellite EO, in situ and citizen science, short-range remote sensing, drones, etc. whilst clearly identifying the purpose of individual data collections to guide their correct use.
- Harmonise and standardise the service documentation, metadata, products and delivery system among different Copernicus Services and downstream services (D2.2, D3.2, D3.3) to ensure users are aware of the complete portfolio of products.

- Encourage the discovery of relevant products hosted across services: examples of good practice are products of the Emergency Management Service (CEMS) made available in the Climate Data Store (CDS) of C3S. In contrast, land cover/land use from the CDS are not found in the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS). Distinctions between climate records and operational products should not obscure findability. (D3.2)

G4: Top-level requirements for a thematic water product collection

Several of the coordination and capacity building requirements identified in Water-ForCE work to date (see e.g., WP1 reports, and D6.3) point to the need to thematically bundle service components. The Copernicus Thematic Hubs (CTH) are an existing initiative to regroup, under one single entry point, information generated by several Copernicus Services for a given high level topic. The planned establishment of a Copernicus Coastal Thematic Hub (CCTH) under the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS), in collaboration with several other Copernicus Services and implemented by EU institutions in close collaboration with Member States national authorities, is a very good opportunity to test whether this approach is a reasonable way forward in other domains like (inland) water. A Copernicus Water Thematic Hub (CWTH) would be a response to the fragmentation and scattered presence of water products within the Copernicus programme and thus provide context to gather user requirements, supply prototypes and evaluate new products resulting from R&D activities. However, isolated thematic hubs for coastal (CCTH) and (inland) water (CWTH) could be at odds with the objective to provide continuity from inland to ocean products, which is important in studying the water, carbon and energy cycle. So, some duplication of products in the catalogues of separate hubs would likely be needed. This, in turn, means that such products would need to find a way to harmonise the requirements from multiple thematic domains. As a starting point, however, establishing a thematic collection based on the CCTH analogue could represent a viable path for the inland water sector to crystallise under the Copernicus programme.

To obtain a rich and operational level of integration it is considered important to implement the following in a thematic collection:

- Collect and maintain, in a single catalogue, relevant products and information, to ensure that products of similar nature but stemming from different Copernicus Services can be found and compared in one place, allowing users to select the most appropriate products.
- Accessibility of products across the Copernicus Services through a common search mechanism (see WP1 outputs and D2.2, D3.2), with search functionality extending from keywords to area of interest (including map-based selection), spatiotemporal resolution, latency, etc. Thematic filters should then be added to results. The CMEMS and C3S portals are considered examples of good practice.
- Harmonise the included products and provide user guidance and support, with the help of the contributing Copernicus Services.
- Facilitate status monitoring at water body level, including water quantity and quality data integrated with local sensor data (see D3.3).
- Following identification of the intended user base, co-design should be evident during the initial 1-year proof-of-concept phase.

Thematic data collections may also function as a platform to locate and initiate capacity building objectives through specific actions:

- Providing and hosting training sessions at all levels (policymakers, water managers, remote sensing scientists, end users).
- Act as a starting point to engage with specific user communities to increase their awareness and uptake of Copernicus data and products and services. (WP1, D2.2)

Innovation

Finally, thematic data collections would have potential to reach beyond the immediate scope of the Copernicus water services, answering widely heard calls to aid users in suitable product selection, regardless of whether these are Copernicus products or generated elsewhere. The following items may be considered Innovation requirements for thematic data collections:

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- Making regional products from nations / member states' monitoring systems available (D3.3)
- Linking with the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) portals and activities (e.g., bathymetry, seabed habitats, chemistry) (D3.3)
- Acting as harmonisation framework across satellite EO, in situ and citizen science, proximal sensing, drone-based campaigns, etc. (WP1).

Last but not least, thematic data collections could provide a platform for research and user communities, to interact to:

- Coordinate development of new remote sensing and modelled products in order to avoid duplication between the Services
- Ensure increased support of EU policies
- Ensure that the in situ component of Copernicus services can validate all current and forthcoming water quantity and water quality related products and provide uncertainties with each of the products.

The last two sets of actions would require extensive user and feasibility study, and embrace the concept of multi-source analytics to meet user demand for situational awareness in water management. The functionality would benefit from support across public programmes (at least Copernicus, EEA) at national and European scales, in collaboration with the private sector through downstream services development.

Water-ForCE will analyse in the Roadmap what kind of organisational structure will be the most optimal to solve the issues and recommendations described above and provide water-related services to different stakeholders and user communities.

Coordination

Research

Innovation

Trust

3.2. [A] Actions required across multiple thematic domains

In addition to the general requirements cutting across the Copernicus water service elements, we have identified four types of action that cut across the thematic application

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domains. These four types broadly align with the Coordination, Research, Innovation and Trust building categorisation:

- A1: Coordination with the in situ data community
- A2: Service evolution and expansion through Research and Development
- A3: Innovation on multi-source, multi-scale observation and integration
- A4: Enhanced confidence through satellite calibration and validation

Coordination**A1: Coordination with the in situ data community**

This set of actions calls for increased Coordination of a relatively fragmented community of experts collecting in situ observations for purposes which are usually isolated from the Copernicus services. Problem areas are listed below, whereas detailed recommended actions are provided (without analysis) in the Appendix. Some of the recommendations are repeated under the Research and Innovation actions recommended in the subsections to follow, where there is clear overlap. The problem areas pertaining to lack of coordination with the in situ data community are:

- A lack of in situ data across the inland to coastal water continuum.
- A specific lack of radiometric data (optical, thermal) to validate upstream products.
- A lack of in situ observations designed to coincide with satellite overpasses, and pre-processed and formatted to facilitate satellite product calibration and validation, ideally provided as a dynamic data service.
- A need to recover data from project-based repositories.
- No data discovery and lack of accessibility from closed repositories.
- Lack of machine-readability for automated data gathering.

The full list of recommendations in the Appendix contains over 20 individual suggestions ranging from efforts to better align the activities of in situ data producers, consumers and end-users, to improvement of data management practices. General priorities are to improve availability and accessibility of in situ data for product calibration and validation,

establishing dedicated calibration and validation sites, and to harmonise how reflectance products are generated for coastal and inland waters.

Research

A2: Service evolution and expansion through Research and Development

Experts and users called for a number of improvements to the current services which directly involve Research and Development effort. In addition to the priorities highlighted below, 16 additional recommended actions are listed in the Appendix. These include a number of actions to support increased hydrological modelling capabilities, with further detail provided in reports D5.2 and D5.3, whilst recommendations stemming from stakeholder engagement in WP1 also highlight the need for holistic watershed modelling from small streams to entire basins and their connectivity to the sea, and recommend dedicated services/sources for water level, altimetry, and bathymetry.

Priority Actions

Table 1 Priority actions within theme A2, in order of maturity. TRL/IRL = Technology / Implementation Readiness Level. References given as 'Dx.y' refer to earlier deliverables in the Water-ForCE project, where additional detail may be found.

Priority action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
A2.1: Improve spatial and temporal resolution of water quality products (D2.2)	8	5		S2 constellation size. The adjacency effect downgrades quality of observations near shore (small water bodies).
A2.2: Faster and easier access to Copernicus and other RS data and products for modelling (D5.1)	8	5		Review user needs for new product development and sensor requirements.
A2.3: Provide uncertainties associated with existing products (D2.2)	5	2	FRM projects, radiometric uncertainty being added to L1 products.	Data scarcity for uncertainty characterisation

A2_4: Regular observations on river dynamics and especially river runoff, transboundary waters and interfaces with seas/oceans. (WP1)	4	3	e.g. Congo river project (Uni of Marseille)	Positioning of river gauges with respect to altimeter tracks.
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Analysis

The first three priority actions would support a wider scope of downstream use of data from the Services. A2_1 can be theoretically achieved (for optical monitoring) by expanding the scope of the Sentinel-2 mission with additional sensors to reduce revisit times. To satisfy the recommendation for improved spatial resolution there are possibilities to enhance the suitability of the Sentinel-2 optical instrument for water, such that the 10-m resolution offered by the sensor (possibly increased to 5-m resolution in future) can capture water quality features in the same manner that ocean colour satellites achieve for larger bodies of water. This requires a set of additional, and potentially narrower wavebands in the visible domain, while taking into account that the signal-to-noise criteria for water (a comparatively dark observation target) must also be met, and the current high resolution optical missions (Sentinel-2) have sub-optimal glint avoidance. The requirement for higher resolution of observations (spatial and temporal) is also featured in many of the additional recommendations listed in the Appendix, cutting across water quality and quantity themes. For coastal water quality, a resolution of chlorophyll-*a* products < 1km is mentioned, possibly being fulfilled with the HR-OC methodology (pending wider validation). A commonly requested target for daily hydrological products is < 1km, as mentioned for soil moisture, surface runoff, river discharge, and snow melt. The technical feasibility of these goals requires further study.

Improved data access for the modelling community (A2_2) requires adopting the state of the art for data visualisation and FAIR data throughout the relevant Copernicus catalogues. Research and development are then needed to complement these catalogues with products which are currently lacking, not provided at appropriate scales, or pending

validation to fulfil regional or global monitoring objectives. There is, therefore, an urgent need to review user needs for new product development and associated sensor requirements (for water quality, see D2.5). Past and recent mission additions such as SWOT should be brought into the Copernicus catalogue (e.g., as a Copernicus contributing mission) for hydrological studies, which is a coordination action for Copernicus and space agencies.

Provision of product uncertainties (A2_3) is already a requirement for products included in the ESA CCI and C3S, and a clearly expressed need by (prospective) users of Copernicus water products. Procedures should be added and documented consistently to the full suite of Copernicus products. However, where uncertainty characterisation relies on in situ data, lack of such data or geographic biases pose challenges (see A1 problem areas).

Observations (in situ and remote) for river dynamics, transboundary waters and the coastal interface should also be scaled up as a priority (A2_4), but technological readiness to operate observation networks is still low due the cost involved in purchasing and maintaining a network of sensors (see also D4.2), which may be resolvable through additional R&D aimed to lower the cost of in situ observation solutions. At the same time, lack of a coordinating network for data beyond nation-scale programmes results in a low score on implementation readiness.

Innovation**A3: Innovation on multi-source, multi-scale observations and data integration**

Recommendations under this theme broadly group as Innovation activities, building on existing capabilities or proof of concept, whilst upscaling and global-scale validation may be required. The recommendations given in the Appendix, in addition to the priority actions identified below, include nine actions pertaining to enhancing in situ observations, five regarding the use of new and existing space assets, and three items on improving the integration of in situ and remote observations. TRLs and IRLs were not assessed in detail for this theme. Under the in situ observation theme, actions to harmonize and encourage integration of observations from satellites, drones, citizen science and regular monitoring

are mentioned several times, whilst enhanced autonomy of in situ observations is also encouraged. To aid data integration efforts, AI methods and data assimilation methodologies are encouraged alongside extensive uncertainty characterisation through inter-comparison exercises. These recommendations suggest broad support to establish a (much) higher level of maturity in the collection and use of in situ data within the context of regional and global observation products. Whilst the focus in this section is on Innovation activities this effort requires global coordination, with Copernicus and (space and environment) agencies contributing to their respective domains.

With regard to space assets, the recommendations made in report D2.5 for an extended set of optical satellite wavebands, and for 'land' sensors to meet the radiometric requirements to observe water bodies, should be highlighted. Whilst these are not put forward as priority actions by the expert group, they are separately reported to ESA in the context of the S2 Next Gen specifications. The reason for the sub-priority grading may be that 'bigger, better, faster' is already well embedded in the design philosophy of new spaceborne sensors, and that recent reporting for CEOS (Dekker et al. 2018) has provided extensive input (in part from the wider community of experts) for new sensor specifications.

Alongside investing in new sensors, recommendations to Copernicus from the expert communities point at multisensory / multimission solutions to enhance the spatiotemporal resolutions required to support new applications, suggesting that the Copernicus services should seek collaborations across space agencies for data access to missions such as planned EE12 GALENE, GLIMR, CHIME, SBG, AQUAWATCH and sensors highlight under other themes, such as SWOT.

Priority Actions

Table 2 Priority actions within theme A3.

Priority action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
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A3_1 (space assets) Improve temporal resolution through mission cooperation (e.g., CHIME and SBG).	8	5		Product formats and metadata standards need harmonisation
A3_2 (in situ): Explore UAV with hyperspectral radiometers to obtain surface reflectance (Rrs) at coastal and inland water sites. (D4.4)	4	5	MONOCLE	Need to form a community of practise to bring UAV-based observation to FRM level.
A3_3 (space assets): Remote sensor development to support water quality observation services (D2.5)	3	3	CEOS implementation plan	Likely need constellation of sensors (costly), continuity to be guaranteed through Sentinel programme, inter-agency collaboration.

Analysis

The priority actions should be interpreted as high-level descriptions of the activities which need to be undertaken, grouping several of the more detailed actions listed in the Appendix. A3_1 takes advantage of current and planned space assets which can enhance the services through collaboration agreements. The example highlights the complementarity of CHIME and SBG, whilst other (hyperspectral and other) missions planned by NASA (GLIMR, PACE) and the Australian Aquawatch mission are also relevant. Collaboration ideally goes beyond data and product access, involving European scientists in the definition of mission requirements and validation activities, of which PACE is already a good example. Priority action A3_3 looks beyond the currently planned missions; specific requirements for hyperspectral missions, enhanced temporal and spatial resolution and revisit times, as well as night-time observations, are given in the respective section of the Appendix and report D2.2.

A3_2 is highlighted here due to the pressing lack of inland and near-shore in situ radiometric observations. Whilst autonomous radiometric observation systems are now available on the market (resulting from H2020 projects including EOMORES, MONOCLE, HYPERNETS), to ensure match-ups at specific locations, UAV and handheld equipment are needed to address locations unsuitable for autonomous stations and to address multiple sites with the

same capital investment. The TRL of UAV based solutions is still low in the absence of an accepted, standardised approach for data collection to formatting and dissemination, and a community of practise needs to be formed urgently. Addressing this shortcoming would enable a wide range of improvements (several are listed in the next section), including addressing the land adjacency effect in optical observations, but also furthering validation capabilities for potential new products that often still require larger-scale validation, including but not limited to floating materials, intertidal habitats, flooded areas, and pollution including (macro-)litter.

- Coordination
- Research
- Innovation
- Trust

A4: Enhanced confidence through satellite product calibration and validation

Enhancing the calibration and validation capabilities across the services requires community coordination, capacity building, training and organising funding, but also defines priorities for research, development and innovation actions. Broadly speaking, enhancing the calibration and validation opportunities within the services is prerequisite to adopting new products, particularly at the regional and global scale. The combined actions below are seen to improve the fitness-for-purpose of service products and promote appropriate use, to ultimately generate trust and uptake with end-users. Whilst the actions are designed to improve confidence in the products, the issue of inadequate calibration and validation was consistently reported in working groups, and several new and emerging methodologies should be embraced to see rapid improvement. All recommended actions under this theme are therefore included in the priority list below.

Actions

Table 3 Actions within theme A4.

Actions	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
Data collection priorities				
A4_1: Create, coordinate and harmonise in situ observation networks (D4.2), by	6	3	GLEON, GEO groups, IOCCG protocols.	Existing communities lack focussed initiatives, or

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forming a community-of-practise to standardise network components such as instruments, measurement protocols, and processing (D2.3 Top-10 priorities)				outcomes have not been kept up to date. Standardisation efforts focussed on measurement protocols, not network operation.
A4_2: Deliver long-term funding to support automated measurement networks (D2.3 Priority 1)	n.a.	5	Aeronet-OC	GCOS implementation plan not yet acted on across the inland/coastal environment.
A4_3: Measurement intercomparison exercises and radiometer calibration/characterization to widely adopt Fiducial Reference Measurement standards (D2.3 Top-10 priorities)	8	7	ESA FRM projects, individual research projects	Activities in inland and coastal water bodies are disconnected. No common reporting strategy.
A4_4: Develop global network of automated observation stations across a range of water types to support atmospheric correction validation in coastal and inland waters, including radiometry and supporting optical-biochemical observations (D2.3 Priority 2)	6	5	Individual (short-lived) research projects. HYPERNETS, EOMORES, MONOCLE	Lack of funding. General policy of Copernicus to not contribute to in situ data collection. Cost of instrument mobility for calibration, customs procedures, no sufficiently large instrumentation pool to equip key sites for shorter periods. Not all desired variables have suitable automation solutions developed.
A4_5: Scale up autonomous hyperspectral spectroradiometry to collect water-leaving radiance reflectance, including facilitating use in regular monitoring programmes.	8	5	Individual (short-lived) research projects. HYPERNETS, EOMORES	Cost of instrument mobility for calibration, customs procedures, no sufficiently large instrumentation pool
A4_6: Develop centralised data services (calibration, handling, reduction, processing, quality control, uncertainty,	3-8	3-8	Largely achieved for satellite data services	Largely lacking for in situ data, and for non-standard satellite derived products or

archiving, distribution) (D2.3 Top-10 priorities)				intermediate processing levels.
A4_7: Develop open-source tools and open access to in situ data (including uncertainty estimation) for validation of atmospheric correction (D2.3 Top-10 priorities)	7	4	FRM projects developing community processor for ocean colour radiometry.	No joint-up international effort for data curation and access.
A4_8: Increase 'satellite literacy' with key agencies to promote more support for remote sensing cal-val (D2.2)	n.a.		GEO Aquawatch, GEOGLOWS initiatives, ESA EO4SDG	National focus likely needed, no one-fits-all solution. Harmonization of formats and meta-data urgently needed.
Hydrology				
A4_9: Enhanced validation of water quantity products (D5.2)				Limited by slow access to non-aggregated, open license in situ data.
Atmospheric correction - specific actions				
A4_10: Coordinate and support atmospheric correction (and adjacency effect correction) round robin exercises for AC validation under a wide range of atmospheric and water conditions (D2.2, D2.3 Top-10 priorities)	7	6	ACIX-Aqua ESA FRM projects Research projects AERONET-OC	In situ data collection efforts require high degree of automation to capture all atmospheric conditions. Sustained funding lacking.
A4_11: Improve algorithms for atmospheric correction (including adjacency correction) of inland and coastal water systems. (D2.2; D2.3 Priority 3)	6	9	Several algorithms actively being developed by (European) research teams	Limited by funding and access to in situ FRM radiometry data. No activities in Copernicus to support radiometric data collection. Absence of in situ radiometry networks.
A4_12: Characterise uncertainties in AC due to algorithm, sensor, water type,	7	4	Combinations of water-leaving radiance and atmospheric	Requires concerted effort to collect transect and stationary data over long

<p>observation angle, adjacency effects, atmospheric composition (D2.3 Top-10 priorities)</p>		<p>characterisation instrument (e.g., HYPERNETS, EOMORES, MONOCLE), UAV mounted sensors, automated shipborne radiometry and simultaneous atmospheric composition characterisation (MONOCLE)</p>	<p>periods. Requires scaling up of new sensors to study observation angle effects. Limited by funding and access to in situ FRM radiometry, particularly near-shore transects requiring boats and/or drone based observation to characterise adjacency effects.</p>
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Analysis

Priorities A4_01 to A4_07 are complementary actions to build up a sustained observation capability, which would clearly benefit from sustained funding to operate in situ observation networks, train new members, provide technical support and to coordinate calibration, measurement and data analysis protocols. Whilst this effort is best coordinated at international level, sustained practises are also recommended within Copernicus to (help) collect the required in situ validation records that would support uncertainty characterisation in all Copernicus water products. This can be through efforts to coordinate the appropriate collection (satisfying the needs of satellite product validation) and use of data sets to validate Copernicus products, including where there is overlap with existing monitoring programmes.

A fundamental issue arises in the case of in situ radiometry (at least for colour and temperature products) where there is data scarcity, no clear objective for national agencies to participate in data collection (as radiometry does not appear in the WFD / MSFD monitoring methodologies), and a need to validate both L1 (top of atmosphere) and L2 (atmospherically corrected) radiometric products. Arguably the validation of L1 radiometry

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is the responsibility of the space agencies, on a per-sensor basis. At the L2 processing stage the responsibility for validation is shared between space agencies and Copernicus services, both of which produce L2 aquatic reflectance products for specific domains.

The ocean and lake colour and temperature variables are Essential Climate Variables and GCOS has identified a need to '[A1] Ensure necessary levels of long-term funding support for in situ networks, from observations to data delivery' as priority action in their 2022 Implementation plan, assigning responsibility for the action to the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and National Meteorological and Hydrological Services (NMHS), Research Organisations, Academia, Funding agencies and GCOS. Then, the action '[B1] Development of reference networks (in situ and satellite Fiducial Reference Measurement (FRM) programs)' is identified as joint responsibility of WMO/NMHS, Space Agencies, Research Organisations, Funding agencies and GCOS. The Copernicus services cannot be easily defined within the categories of Responsible bodies set in the Implementation plan, but logically fall between 'Global Data Centres' and 'Space Agencies' when looking at their activities and outputs.

These first recommendations largely originate from work reported in report D2.3. A community-of-practise does not formally exist and should be formed, while in situ data and EO expertise do exist with current members of FRM initiatives, GLEON, GEO Aquawatch, ACIX initiatives, among others. The activities should be seen as a continuum starting with the formation and evolution of observation network nodes to contribute to calibration and validation datasets, filling gaps (e.g., optical and thermal radiometry), harmonising procedures and data management, whilst working on a portfolio of training and technical support to build support with national agencies (A4.08). Given the importance of product validation in the Services, and the needs for new products reported in this document, it should be obvious that concerted effort is warranted across a range of actors including the Core Services, the space agencies, national agencies, GCOS, the scientific community, and relevant sectors of industry (e.g. water utilities). In recent years, several FRM projects have seen support through space agencies to improve in situ observation methods and validate

ocean/water colour post atmospheric correction, and (to a lesser extent) water skin temperature. Several EU funded projects (HYPERNETS, EOMORES, MONOCLE) designed instruments specifically for optical radiometric calibration and validation of satellite products of aquatic and land targets. Thus, with suitable instrumentation available on the market, these processes are ready for upscaling to the requirements of the services. An additional set of coordination and innovation actions is still required to mainstream good practices and bring these into the domain of regular monitoring efforts, and to engage global communities such as GLEON to do the same.

Priority A4.10, to coordinate round-robin exercises informing the selection of atmospheric correction solutions, has been covered in recent years through the Atmospheric Correction Intercomparison Exercise (ACIX-Aqua) collaboration driven by developers of atmospheric correction routines and supported by ESA, NASA, and in situ radiometric data producers, although largely without dedicated funding for the latter. The latest exercise was unable to demonstrate adequate performance over all wavebands and optical water types for any given algorithm for the high resolution Sentinel-2 MSI sensor, but several codes remain in active development and validation within the Copernicus land service has shown improved results. Current research should extend to identifying situations where the uncertainty of the atmospherically corrected reflectance is high, such as with adjacent land and across turbidity gradients. Given the importance of analysis-ready aquatic reflectance procedures and datasets using one or more atmospheric correction routines, expansion of this activity to cover priorities A4.11 (including adjacency effect correction) and A4.12 is highly recommended to improve data quality in optically challenging environments (particularly inland and near-shore) and requires progress on data collection techniques. At the same time, ESA are now committed to producing an analysis ready L2 aquatic reflectance product in Sen2Water, which conforms to the state of the art used across the services for optical water quality. The community of practice for these activities should include present contributors as well as novel observation platform experts (e.g., drones) to fulfil the

expanded data requirements, and could benefit from organising as an international working group (e.g. under GEO Aquawatch).

Priority A4_9 is still poorly defined and requires further input from operational hydrological networks, monitoring and modelling experts.

Research

3.3. [B] Management and hazards

Innovation

The general recommendations included under this theme in the Appendix list a range of domains where the portfolio of products should be expanded through a combination of observation and modelling, to ultimately contribute to a better response to hazards, and one that is more widely adopted. The impact of products of adequate resolution to support the assurance/insurance industry is also mentioned, both in the short time scale (highlighted below as a priority) and at longer timescales (to assess risk). In some cases, uptake of Copernicus products in emergency response has been slow due to lack of documentation or lack of training to use the data interfaces provided.

Priority Actions

Table 4 Priority actions within theme B.

Priority action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
B_1: Develop sea-river and groundwater-river interaction products (D3.2)	3	2		Research activities are fragmented
B_2: Develop water quality and water levels (quantity) of smaller reservoirs and rivers at catchment scale (WP1)	6	6	Ongoing R&D projects, ESA CCI	Land adjacency effects in optical imagery to be resolved. Lack of in situ data.
B_3: Provide near real-time flooding and immediate risks at scales relevant to the assurance and insurance sector (WP1)	5	5		Very high resolution observations need to be fully exploited and accessible for research, including non-Sentinel missions.

Analysis

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The priority actions reflect a need to expand the scope of applicability of the service products, reducing latency and increasing spatial resolution, resolving interaction areas between rivers and groundwater at one end, and ultimately with sea areas (see also section A2). This will require resolving smaller water bodies including streams, or at least the contribution of streams in the catchment as a whole, which may be inferred from a combination of observation time series and modelling. However, the physical constraints of resolving properties of water in the vicinity of land remain a clearly needed research focus (see also section A4).

In addition to priority B_1, report D3.2 details a number of expansions to the product portfolio to support the systematic assessment of risks related to droughts and flooding, across a wide range of TRLs. This clearly marks a focus area for the development of the Services as well as the underlying space assets (gravimetric mission continuity).

Research

3.4. [C] Management and environment, water accounting

Innovation

Under the Space Programme Regulation (EU) 2021/696, acceptable activities for Copernicus and its services must include novel use cases for water management, as well as inland water quality and quantity monitoring. This is, therefore, considered a core domain where Copernicus is expected to deliver through upstream and downstream service delivery. Industries interviewed further indicated that shifting towards a water-smart society reflecting the true economic value of water, can be enabled by new digital water technologies to optimise management of water resources.

It is key that priority actions under this theme which require coordination include furthering the uptake of remote sensing products in the WFD. This should include (1) supporting the newly formed ECOSTAT WG to establish a common approach to using satellite products in WFD reporting, notably on phytoplankton bloom intensity (Papathanasopoulou et al. 2019) (WP1), and (2) furthering these efforts to improve the effectiveness of the WFD to tackle water scarcity (Apostolaki et al. 2019) (D3.3). As in earlier sections, exploiting data from

Coordination

SWOT missions to improve river flows and lake storage monitoring is considered a priority to improve resilience (D3.3).

The priority actions for research and innovation are listed below, with 25 additional R&D, innovation, coordination and trust-enhancing actions included in the Appendix.

Priority Actions

Table 5 Priority actions within theme C.

Priority action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
New or expanded products				
C_1: Observation/modelling of primary productivity, nutrient availability (D2.2; D2.4)	3	2	Various research projects	Scarce in situ data availability for PP product validation. Nutrient availability only achievable through in situ observation and/or modelling.
C_2: Chlorophyll-a concentration in <u>all</u> inland waters (lakes, reservoirs, rivers). (WP1)	7	7	Copernicus Land Service Water Quality to include chlorophyll-a in 4265 water bodies at 300m resolution, limited set of S2 tiles included at 100m resolution. A research focus worldwide.	Resolving all water bodies requires the use of S2 MSI at larger scale at its highest resolution. Limited confidence in Chl-a products in small water bodies due to land adjacency effects. Lack of validation data from large variety of lake types
C_3: Add water quality indicators with high TRL for global detection, for example but not limited to Phycocyanin as proxy for cyanobacteria in inland waters. (D2.2 D2.4)	7	2	Feasibility studies exist including AI based models which can outperform past physics-based approaches. Detection levels may be high,	Limited observation capability using current high resolution sensors, excluding smaller water bodies. See also C_7. Lack of in situ data for verification.

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			requiring alignment of the product with user requirements.	
C_4 Data on storage and flows of inland waters (rivers and lakes)	4	1	SWOT mission	Lack of ground truthing and bathymetry
C_5: Groundwater: storage change or total water storage change (D5.1)	2	1	Partially achieved with NASA GRACE at global scale. R&D on Lake Storage Change from altimetry in ESA Lakes_cci.	Only relative change is currently observed.
Decision support				
C_6: Digital Twins, Decision Support Systems, GIS-based knowledge management systems for decision making (WP1)				Limited activity on digital catchment twins compared to oceans, regional seas.
Space assets and mission collaboration				
C_7: Sentinel-2 E wavebands enabling delivery of new biogeochemical products, in terms of radiometric and spectral resolution. Bands centred at 470, 620, 810, and 1070 nm are highlighted (D2.2, D2.4, Action C_3)	4	2	Active ESA working group on S2E technical characteristics. Water-ForCE input (2022) on water quality community requirements (four new spectral bands).	Inclusion of new bands on mixed land/water missions require broad justification (D2.4).
C_8: Exploitation of (future) hyperspectral satellite missions for water (e.g., CHIME, PACE) alongside European initiatives.	n.a.	n.a.	Two decades of experimental hyperspectral missions.	Limited hyperspectral water reflectance from inland and coastal waters for product development and validation. Lack of harmonisation in metadata standards between agencies.
C_9: HR thermal band is needed for monitoring evapotranspiration. Waiting	n.a.	n.a.	ESA Sen-ET	Sentinel-3 spatial resolution insufficient for key

for the LSTM Expansion mission, Landsat TIR is needed.				applications (e.g., water consumption in croplands)
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Analysis

The priority research and innovation actions focused on the inclusion of new products include those which would help deliver the WFD (C_2, C_3) and expand the set of biogeochemical observations to primary productivity via combined observation and modelling (C_1). The science behind observing a larger number of biogeochemically relevant products than those currently included in the service (notably skin temperature, chlorophyll-a, turbidity) already spans several decades, and there are several products at mid to high TRL, whilst lacking global validation due to sparse in situ reference observations (resulting in lower IRL). The highlighted phycocyanin product (part of C_3) is a typical but non-exhaustive example, supporting the WFD element of quantifying phytoplankton composition (at group level) and risk management (potential toxicity and harm to wildlife and humans). Upscaling mature products for inclusion in the services is an Innovation action, whilst those with lower TRL should be considered priority R&D.

To support the development of new biogeochemical products across inland and coastal water a combination of medium and high-resolution optical sensors is recommended throughout the Water-ForCE analysis documents. High-resolution optical satellite capabilities are found to lack observation capability in the 470, 620, 810, and 1070 nm wavebands found on equivalent medium resolution sensors (D2.4). The 1070 nm band is necessary for atmospheric correction in turbid waters and thus supports all optical water quality products, and useful in detecting floating material on waters (buoyant cyanobacteria, macroalgae, pollen, litter, foam, plastic, macrophytes). The specific recommendation to introduce high-TRL biogeochemical products to the service is therefore closely linked to C_7, which would see new wavebands added to the next generation of Sentinel-2 instruments. This also links to the recommendation to exploit (future) hyperspectral missions (C_8) resulting in multi-mission products (WP1 recommendations). Report D2.4 provides further consideration on the potential improvement of multispectral sensors.

The R&D requirements in this theme are closely linked to issues of scale mentioned in section A4, addressing the physical limitations of remote sensing to resolve small water bodies under all atmospheric conditions, where more insight is still needed.

Fundamental research is needed to further groundwater and total water storage change observation (C_4), to bring the discipline beyond the state of the art represented by the NASA GRACE mission. Furthering this is primarily the domain of the space agencies.

Transforming R&D on catchment observation and modelling to evolve into Digital Twins, and furthering the development of Digital Twins to support decision making from regional to supra-regional scales, will require dedicated funding alongside current lighthouse activities. The scale at which funding should be deployed to tackle general issues of developing Digital Twins (such as connecting these to relevant observation data from Copernicus) versus regional specifics, should be carefully considered, with a view to effectively engage stakeholders at the appropriate regional and national levels in co-development.

Research

3.5. [D] Food and water security (including climate resilience)

Innovation

Most of the twelve recommendations under this theme relate to delivery of products to reduce cost and assure high quality in water supply, including groundwater and modelling of food security risks.

The recommendations in this theme were not analysed in terms of priority or maturity but an overview is provided here regardless.

For open water bodies, prominent recommendations are to

- conduct R&D into developing Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter products and relatedly, Dissolved Organic Carbon, to assist drinking water resource and water effluent monitoring.

- Deliver a suite of products to monitor water quality in shallow waters, primary production, litter including micro and macroplastic, and indicator pigments in areas used for water supply.

Providing information to monitor groundwater aquifers was highlighted as a priority action by experts consulted in WP1, with an estimated current TRL and IRL of 4. To support monitoring and modelling of groundwater, it is further advised to:

- Couple groundwater level monitoring to land use change (WP1)
- Resolve soil moisture profiles / soil water balance (D3.3, D5.2)
- Detect soil salinization (WP1)

For water resource modelling, recommendations are made to resolve river cross sections, hydraulic structures, and reservoir geometries (D3.4).

The full list of recommended RDI actions is provided in the Appendix.

Research

3.6. [E] Transport

Two requirements which came out of WP1 consultations can be grouped under this theme, which was not explored at the same level of detail within Water-ForCE as other themes:

- risk-related indices to water systems: congestion, fishing jetties, flow speed, overgrowth, subsidence, sedimentation.
- monitoring of fast-growing water plants and algae that could hinder vessel movement on inland waterways (see also D2.4).

Whilst both aspects have clear economic impact, neither were considered priority actions within the broader thematic analysis carried out by the Water-ForCE consortium.

Analysis

Other than for the observation of suspended sediments and floating vegetation, fundamental research would be needed to determine the other factors posing risks in this sector, exploiting a combination of high resolution radar and optical imagery. The revisit

times and spectral resolution of current high resolution sensors, mentioned several times under other themes, would also pose limitations here, with multi-mission solutions including very-high resolution data part of a potential solution. Satellite-derived bathymetry would provide obvious support for development in this theme and is currently absent in Copernicus.

Coordination

3.7. [F] Environmental Climate Variable (ECV) monitoring

Research

The requirements for ECV monitoring are set by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), following expert input through relevant panels such as the Terrestrial Observation Panel for Climate (TOPC) and Ocean Observations Physics and Climate Panel (OOPC). During the Water-ForCE requirements inventory and industry expert interviews, a number of ECVs were indicated as priorities for the Services. Given that they are all actively addressed in the ESA Climate Change Initiatives, they are listed here only as Coordination priorities, because product availability to the Copernicus user base is established through C3S which does not currently host the full set of ECVs for which satellite EO methods are developed in the ESA Climate Change Initiative. It is noted that the timeliness of product delivery is a clear distinction between the operational Services (CLMS, CMEMS), the periodically updated C3S, and the R&D-driven CCI programme.

Establishing the full set of ECVs and making these widely accessible is considered a priority action. The availability across the services and CCI of the ECVs marked as most important are indicated in Table 6. Numerous differences exist between the products, resolution, methodologies (sensors included, algorithms used) between the services, which are not detailed here.

Table 6 Product availability across the CCI and Copernicus services for highlighted essential climate variables

Essential Climate Variable	ESA CCI	Copernicus C3S	Copernicus Land	Copernicus Marine
Surface water temperature				
- Sea	Included	Included	-	85 products
- Lakes	Included	Included	Included	-

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Lake water extent	Included	Not included	2 products	-
Lake water level	Included	Included	Included	-
Lake / coastal colour	Included	Not included	Included	4 products for coastal waters
Sea ice extent	Included	Reanalysis	-	Included
Lake ice extent	Included	Not included	2 products	-
Lake ice thickness	Included (ramp-up)	Not included	Not included	-
Glaciers	Included	2 sources	Not included	-

The following products are not (yet) considered ECVs by GCOS, but were also brought up in the context of climate monitoring priorities, and should be considered additional R&D actions:

- Primary productivity
- Algal bloom phenology (ocean, coastal and inland)
- Methane emissions
- Aquatic carbon fractions

In addition, a recommendation to produce snowmelt, and ice extent products at finer resolution (< 1km) was made in the context of (climate) modelling studies (D5.2).

4. Conclusions

4.1. Elaborating the challenge areas

The recommendations derived from the Water-ForCE consultation phase generally corroborate the main challenge areas marked at the start of this document, where we can now elaborate several RDI priority areas as follows:

Fragmentation in data and gaps in the product portfolio, such that the needs of data brokers and end-users across sectors are not fully met

- The general recommendations for a thematic collection [G4], in the form of thematic hubs or other, show that fragmented product offerings form an obstacle to uptake

for a range of experts and stakeholders. Some users were not aware of the existence of products which they considered to be lacking [G3], which therefore requires better presentation and findability of products across the services, as well as more emphasis on outreach and training.

- There are significant gaps in the product portfolio which need to be resolved for and with the hydrological, biogeochemical, and climate modelling communities.

Water quantity related improvements include:

- Sea-river and groundwater-river interaction products (B_1)
- Groundwater storage change or total water storage change (C_4)
- Water quality and water level of smaller reservoirs, rivers (B_2)
- Near real-time flooding risk at 10-1000m scales (B_3)
- Soil moisture profiles / soil water balance (D)
- Soil salinization (D)
- A full set of ECVs (F)

Regular observations on river dynamics and especially river runoff, transboundary waters and interfaces with seas/oceans are, also generally found lacking (A2_4).

The RDI requirements are extensive and point to a combination of observation, modelling and data integration techniques needing to be developed. Multi-mission collaboration across space agencies should be encouraged.

Water quality related improvements include:

- Water quality and water level of smaller reservoirs, rivers (B_2)
- Observation/modelling of primary productivity, nutrients (C_1)
- Chlorophyll-a concentration of all water bodies (C_2)
- Phycocyanin concentration in lakes, reservoirs, rivers (C_3)
- Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter (Dissolved Organic Carbon proxy) (D, F).
- Optical water quality variables in shallow waters (D)

- Primary production or productivity (D, F)
 - Litter (D)
 - Indicator pigments (plankton and benthos) (D)
 - A full set of ECVs (F)
 - Algal bloom phenology (ocean, coastal and inland) (F)
- There is still a lack of support to develop Digital Twins, Decision Support Systems, and GIS-based knowledge management systems for decision making across the land-water continuum (C_5)

Limited (trust in) product quality of inland water variables

- Urgent action is required to validate and improve the fitness-for-purpose of inland water (quality and quantity) variables. Despite increased capabilities in space assets, several issues blocking product uptake are currently evident:
- Product uncertainties are not widely provided (A2_3)
 - In situ validation networks and communities of practise are not appropriately organised and funded and lack radiometric components (A4_1-7)
 - High-frequency automated observations are not sufficiently promoted and funded (A4_2)
 - Water quantity is not sufficiently/operationally validated (A4_9)

Shortcomings are most severely felt around small water bodies and rivers, which due to lack of validation activities and challenging observation conditions near land remain largely out of scope of actionable water products. Research is needed to improve atmospheric correction in these conditions (A4_10-12), and new technologies (automation, UAVs, citizen science) can be upscaled within appropriate networks. Of course, improving the accessibility, availability and suitability of past and present in situ reference observations is also prerequisite to filling several gaps in the product portfolio (see previous item).

- In parallel with the required improvements in product quality and validation, capacity building and 'mainstreaming' with key agencies is required to build support for contributions to remote sensing calibration and validation (A4_8).

Lack of integration of products and services to achieve a coherent and consistent inland water monitoring system

- This challenge has the broadest of the three that are highlighted here, and links closely to the existence of data gaps and product validation issues described above. In contrast to those fundamental challenges, integration of data typically takes place at a higher level, by and for a range of downstream data brokers ideally serving a wide range of sectors. Integration of products across disciplines is largely the domain of data analytics, data assimilation and modelling. Product uncertainties, compatible formats (grid resolution, aggregation intervals), and gap-filling techniques should therefore be defined from this end-user perspective whilst data access should be streamlined (A2_2). In contrast, the current Service portfolio has a strong element 'technology push' from the remote sensing sciences.
- The problem areas listed under theme A1 corroborate this challenge. In particular, continuity of products from inland to coastal areas is found lacking, while data discoverability and accessibility is an issue. Integration across the in situ, satellite and modelling components so the water monitoring system is needed.
- The needs of the hydrological, biogeochemical and climate modelling communities are insufficiently met. This is partly due to data gaps and fragmentation (see above), and partly because integration between in situ observation networks and the Service components is poorly facilitated. The recommendations under theme G2 call for better data platforms that support multi-source analytics to improve situational awareness in the water sector, including smart technologies. Recommended actions under theme G2 and A1 also call for continuity in effort between Earth observation, proximal sensing with drones, and developing citizen science

components, whilst encouraging national monitoring bodies to implement strategic monitoring sites to better integrate with a holistic observing system.

4.2. Elaborating the RDI solutions

We can now also further elaborate the solution areas where RDI activities are needed.

Develop high-level biogeochemical products

- Realise the list of priority products (see Fragmentation challenge in section 4.1 and details provided in WP2, 3 and 5 deliverables for water quality, quantity and modelling).

Upscaling mid to high TRL products which have been locally or regionally demonstrated requires regional to global validation before entering into Copernicus services. This step is used to characterise product uncertainties, to apply state-of-the-art methodology at global scale within acceptable uncertainty bounds. Those bounds may be defined by water body morphology, optical characteristics, seasonality or a combination thereof. Table 7 provides an overview of all biogeochemical products referenced in the Water-ForCE documentation, and whether they link to primary policy (WFD, MSFD, etc.) or industry needs, the SDGs, or the ECVs. This table is presented without prioritisation, recognising that many of the observable products exist at similar TRL.

Table 7 Recommended biogeochemical products and links to policy, industry, SDGs and ECVs. Product categories are not mutually exclusive. Remote sensing observation potential is marked positive (+) when direct observations or observation proxies are proven diagnostic, negative (-) where no direct observation or diagnostic proxy exists, or neutral (0) when diagnosticity is likely situation dependent.

Product	Remote observation potential	Links				Water-ForCE Reports
		Policy	Industry	SDG	ECV	
Eutrophication, aquatic health						
Trophic status	+			X		D1.6
Chlorophyll-a (phytoplankton)	+	X		X		D1.4, D1.6
Phycocyanin (cyanobacteria)	+	X	X	X		D1.4, D2.2
Bloom frequency	+	X		X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.2
Nitrogen fractions and TN	-	X		X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.4
Phosphorus fractions and TP	-	X		X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.4

Water-ForCE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020-research and innovation programme under grant agreement number: 101004186.

Dissolved oxygen	-			X		D1.6
Toxins	-					D1.6
Light, erosion, habitats and biodiversity						
Submerged vegetation (cover or biomass)	0	X				D2.4
Turbidity	+	X		X		D1.4, D1.6
Suspended matter	+					D1.6, SDG, D2.2
Transparency	+	X				
Light attenuation	+	X		X		D1.6, D2.2
Plankton size, func. groups, pigments	0	X		X		D1.6, D2.2
Benthic habitats	0	X		X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.2, D2.4
Floating matter						
Plants (e.g. water hyacinth)	+					D1.6, SDG, D2.4
Litter (macro, aggregated)	+					D2.4
Macroalgae (<i>Sargassum</i> , <i>Ulva</i>)	+	X				D2.4
Pollen	0					D2.4
Climate (incl. modelling)						
Total inorganic carbon	-					D2.4
Total organic carbon	-					D2.4
Particulate organic carbon	-					D2.4
Dissolved Organic Matter composition (incl. UV absorption slope)	0		X			D1.4, D2.2
Coloured DOM	+		X	X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.4
Dissolved organic carbon	-		X			D1.4, D2.4
Lake/ocean colour (reflectance)	+				X	
Benthic carbon	-					D2.4
Benthic primary production	-					D2.4
Primary productivity	0			X		D1.6, D1.6, D2.2, D2.4
Greenhouse gases (CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O)	+		X		X	D1.6, D2.4
Pollutants						
Microbial contaminants	-		X	X		D1.6
Metals	-	X				D1.6
Litter including microplastic	0			X		D1.6
Other						
Particle size distribution	0					D2.2
Bathymetry (optically shallow water)	+	X		X		D1.4, D1.6, D2.4

- Improve in situ observation networks (A4_1-7), encourage monitoring bodies to contribute to strategic data collection for satellite product cal/val (A1, see Appendix)

To support the ongoing validation of existing and new biogeochemical products, we recognize that poor correspondence between in situ and remote sensing water quality indicators is responsible for relatively slow progress, despite local to regional validation of EO methodologies. There are shortcomings to address in both the in situ and remote observation framework:

On the one hand, better coordination and uptake with member states to strategically sample for enhanced satellite product validation is needed to ensure that remotely sensed products can be adequately validated. Radiometry is highlighted several times in this document and should accompany reference observations of biogeochemical quantities wherever feasible or strategic. It is equally important that reference observations target the same properties of biogeochemical substances as those that can be resolved from satellite sensors. For example, comparing pigment absorption across observation scales leads to lower uncertainty than comparing the remotely sensed signal to other expressions of in vivo biomass.

Following the 'mainstreaming' of in situ data collection for satellite validation, R&D into data integration and / or reconstruction methodologies is needed to resolve how conventional sampling and surface water gridded products can be used in management and reporting for the WFD. This work could extend to observations using low-cost equipment and citizen science. Revision of the WFD Common Implementation Strategy may not be required, if the existing elements are demonstrably observed reliably from space.

At the same time, coordination with the remote sensing community to develop actionable water quality indicators that are characterised by low product uncertainty, should receive a strong R&D focus. Examples are variations in water colour or data-driven image classification. This could lead to indicators which could be proposed as new WFD elements (likely requiring revision of the Common Implementation Strategy), or as complementary methodology to address existing elements. Both directions of research require coordination across expert communities in remote sensing, in situ observation and policy/reporting,

potentially by Copernicus in situ and JRC, while the RDI elements can be addressed through dedicated Horizon Europe funding such as in the Green Missions.

Develop mixed EO/modelling approaches to deliver key variables with hindcast and forecast features

- Faster / easier access to Copernicus and other remotely sensed data and products for modelling (A2_2)
- Regular observations on river dynamics and especially river runoff, transboundary waters and interfaces with seas/oceans (A2_4)

Advanced hydrological modelling and forecasting requires regular observation data at appropriate spatial scales. A relatively urgent RDI topic is the development of multi-mission, multi-scale integration of observation data to deliver reliable input to hydrological modelling and forecasting. The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission which is in the validation phase, has been repeatedly mentioned as a disrupting technology. However, a revisit time of 11 days falls short of the critical time window for emergency response, such that a combination of observation strategies (e.g., with Sentinel 3 SAR) is still needed. Being a shared NASA/CNES mission, RDI activities are needed to recommend follow-on and complementary assets within Copernicus through inter-agency collaboration.

Achieve consistency between land and ocean products

- Coordinate and harmonise in situ observation networks, by forming a community-of-practise to standardise network components such as instruments, measurement protocols, and processing (A4_1) and assigning a coordinating body for product and data harmonisation, with appropriate funding.
- Atmospheric correction improvements and harmonisation (A4_10-12)

- Facilitate data analytics and modelling communities, co-design data collections based on their requirements.

From a user perspective, the sheer number of Copernicus products with similar keywords and data properties which nevertheless differ in methodology, is a deterrent to product uptake. This is particularly evident in the Marine Service. Recent research and development (H2020 CERTO, HR-OC) has focussed on harmonisation of methods across the inland to ocean interface for optical water quality products, albeit with validation limited to a few key transitional water bodies. The (prototype / proposed) algorithms resulting from these services require wider validation and could thus lead to products with preferred status. However, product development for optically complex waters is still a fast-moving process, particularly with regard to atmospheric correction. Any change in atmospheric correction output tends to trigger a process of retraining and/or reprocessing in downstream product generation. Regular upgrades and archive reprocessing may thus be needed depending on the scope of the service, with on-demand reprocessing a potentially viable alternative to be offered either within the core services, or as downstream commercial activities. Development of said service elements would be within the remit of any relevant Innovation funding instruments.

Throughout the product improvement cycle, it is essential to adequately characterise product uncertainties. This requires further consideration of downstream users and their requirements for data analytics and modelling. Communities-of-practise tend to form around these requirements, but are currently not well embedded in the Copernicus service process, except for CMEMS In situ TAC which also provides some funding for validation efforts. This issue of funding sustained networks for in situ validation is key, as the services ultimately rely on to quantify product uncertainty. Despite the existence of some communities of practise, the role of a coordinating body to agree on priorities and disseminate funding, is clearly lacking. The most obvious candidate for this role is Copernicus In Situ, which has already commissioned gap analysis, while next steps are not yet clear.

Develop change detection approaches for water availability, water quality, water storage, water fluxes, temperature, lake and river ice and coastal areas

- Couple groundwater level monitoring to land use change (D)
- Resolve river cross sections, hydraulic structures, and reservoir geometries (D)
- Implement and deliver monitoring of all Essential Climate Variables (F)
- Facilitate data analytics platforms with easy access to Copernicus and other data assets (A1, see Appendix)

Priority recommendations in this solution space focus on water and food security and climate resilience, but these form part of a wider range of recommendations extending the impact of Copernicus across the SDGs, and towards industries (e.g., utilities, insurance) which are currently not well served by the available products and services. Part of the solution lies in complementing the product portfolio (including solutions highlighted further above), whereas an R&D component focussed on data analytics, both for the main observation disciplines (water quantity, quality) as well as serving inter-disciplinary objectives (e.g. SDG, climate adaptation and mitigation, change frameworks e.g. DPSIR) which could benefit from enhanced data-driven change analysis. Ideally, analytics would relate land and water change across temporal and spatial scales, whilst also resolving the fine resolution. This requires significant R&D into compatible observation technologies but may be seen as a precursor to successful implementation of Digital Twins in complex hydrological landscapes. R&D is needed on the regional and continental scale, with Horizon Europe RIA a likely funding instrument. Previous and existing actions such as the ESA funded EO4SD placed a strong focus on service deployment and capacity building, which could be useful complementary activities to ensure co-creation of results. There are obvious opportunities to extend the work and deployment of change detection in downstream, including commercial, applications.

Develop innovative methodologies to characterise uncertainties, including in situ data collection and crowdsourcing

- Improving in situ observation networks (A4_1-7)
- Develop networks of fixed stations with hyperspectral radiometers to obtain water reflectance at coastal and inland water sites and explore the possibility to use UAV and ASV surface reflectance across optical gradients at coastal and inland water sites. (A3_2)
- Atmospheric correction (including adjacency correction) improvements (A4_10-12)

Research in this solution space is ongoing, albeit on highly fragmented funding sources and without meaningful investment from the core services. Observation network extension with radiometry would deliver validation data that are relevant for both upstream products (L1, space agencies) and core services (L2, atmospheric correction). The use of uncrewed aerial platforms to resolve land adjacency effect in optical (and thermal) imagery may be considered disruptive, particularly when combining technologies for microscale (typically copters) and extended shoreline (typically fixed wing) observation with suitable payload. Instrument calibration facilities are needed to extend these observations to be compatible with FRM guidelines.

Numerous additional improvements could be made to in situ observation networks, both from the perspective of technology deployment and data management. These require coordinating action (from site selection to training), cross-community involvement (site selection, validation, feedback), and ultimately sustained funding. Accreditation mechanisms may be useful to guide development and funding, which then requires a coordinating body such as Copernicus In Situ.

Strengthen the portfolio of services and products through existing and planned space assets

- Improve spatial and temporal resolution of water quality products (A2_1)
- Mission cooperation (e.g., with NASA CHIME, SBG) (A3_1)

Multi-mission, mixed-resolution and reconstructed (incl. gap-filled) water products may make use of novel downscaling techniques, including novel use of artificial intelligence. For products requiring prior atmospheric correction, multi-mission concepts should consider the whole processing workflow and complementary sensor abilities.

Projects undertaking these investigations would benefit from streamlined data ordering and mission tasking procedures, agreed between space agencies. The actions are suitable to be carried out with direct funding from space agencies or through existing international research programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe RIA).

- Remote sensor development to support water quality services (A3_3, C_7-9)

The development of novel or improved remote sensors is a long-term effort for which ESA procedures exist. R&D preceding mission feasibility studies should prove observation concepts, typically using simulations and in situ or airborne observations. Suitable funding frameworks may include Horizon Europe RIA although relatively smaller (100k-1M€) projects could produce efficient results in smaller teams. The ESA technology programmes offer opportunities to submit proposals through open calls and announcements of opportunity. The role of Copernicus services is mainly to identify requirements from data users and service providers.

5. References

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6. Appendix

This appendix lists all recommended actions that were not primarily grouped within Research and Innovation themes, or not considered among priorities based on urgency, opportunity, or impact by our expert group.

Coordination

A1: Coordination with the in situ data community

Problem areas

- A lack of data across the inland to coastal water continuum
- A specific lack of radiometric data (optical, thermal) to validate upstream products
- A lack of in situ observations designed to coincide with satellite overpasses, and pre-processed and formatted to facilitate satellite product cal-val, ideally provided as a dynamic data service.
- A need to recover data from project-based repositories.
- No data discovery and lack of accessibility from closed repositories.
- Lack of machine-readability for automated data gathering

Actions

Priority actions are listed in Table 8, other actions in Table 9. Specific bottlenecks other than the lack of coordinating frameworks, are listed, as well as any project activities or communities with relevant, recent or current outputs.

Table 8 Priority actions theme A1, in order of maturity. TRL/IRL = Technology / Implementation Readiness Level. References given as 'Dxy' refer to earlier deliverables in the Water-ForCE project, where additional detail may be found.

Action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects, actors etc)	Known bottlenecks
Improve the availability of (in situ) data for calibration and validation activities (D2.2)	6	4	S2VT, S3VT, ESA-Cal-Val, CEOS, GLEON, GLORIA	Funding
Improve storage and accessibility of in situ data	6	4	HYPERNETS, AERONET-OC, GLEON, AQUA-INFRA	Funding
Development of calibration and/or validation sites (especially for inland waters) (D4.4)	5	4	EOMORES, MONOCLE, HYPERNETS	Funding
Harmonise remote sensing reflectance products for coastal and inland waters (D5.2)	2	2	RoundRobin (ACIX)	Lack of consensus

Table 9 Remaining actions under theme A1. Empty elements were not assessed by the expert team.

Action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects, actors etc)	Known bottlenecks
<i>Promote alignment between in situ data producers, consumers and end-users</i>				
Encourage Member states to improve monitoring and assessment tools (D3.3)	7	4	EOMORES (white paper, 2019)	Broad range of requirements between member states.
Coordination between RS and modelling communities to harmonise datasets and reduce uncertainty (D5.1)	7	6	ESA CCI	
Make long-term in situ data collection a shared responsibility between agencies and service providers of satellite data products	6	4	LTER, GCOS	Coordination is still focussed on R&D
Incentivise in situ data producers to produce high-quality data suited to needs of other communities	3	4		Funding
Incentivise data producers to make data openly available.	3	4		
Support long-term sustainability of citizen science initiatives.	3	4	e.g. Secchi disk projects	Uncertainty in long-term funding
<i>Improve (centralised) data management</i>				
Support interaction between networks, communities and bottom-up initiatives such as e.g., GLEON, SeaBASS and LIMNADES,	6	4	GLEON RS Group, GEO AquaWatch	Coordination limited to research groups and activities, no wider stakeholder buy-in
Select and support a designated (meta)data repository for centralised discovery of inland and coastal in situ data repositories.	6	3	AQUA-INFRA, BLUECLOUD	Relatively more advanced in oceanography; non-existent in coastal and inland scope.
Encourage funders to scrutinize project data management including low-latency sharing of environmental observation data and imposing FAIR and TRUST principles, repository standards e.g., “Core Trust Seal” and “Re3” or more specific (D4.3, D4.6)	5	4	Specific project frameworks such as Horizon Europe embracing FAIR principles	
Map the global availability of relevant in situ data for use with satellite-EO data and identify the gaps for different scientific communities.	5	3	GEO AquaWatch, GLORIA	Isolated, ad-hoc activities

Create a seal of quality for Quality Assured / Quality Controlled data (D4.4)	5	3	ICOS, CCI	No common QA/QC criteria
Encourage training of institutional capability for data repository curation and management	3	3		
Stimulate open data sharing and (meta)data standards for data collected from emerging platforms such as Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle imagery and Citizen Science projects (D4.4)	2	2	MONOCLE	
Centralise data curation for emerging data sources, including mechanisms to share UAV imagery (D4.4)	2	2		
Data uncertainty characterization is needed to highlight the performance of any emerging methods and alternative data sources (D4.4)	2	2		
Explore existing repositories to build common coordination frameworks, capacity and flexibility to host new/existing in situ data.	1	2	SeaBass, Limnades	
Discourage the creation of short-term or project-specific data holdings and instead provide support to new users to facilitate their data curation needs.	0	0		
Harmonise data formats across the Copernicus services (D5.1)				
Coordination between EO and AI communities to improve uptake of AI in EO (D5.3)				
Closer cooperation between RS/ Copernicus services and national water monitoring organisations (D5.3)				
Cooperative activities to consider the use of merge data for local water management (D5.3)				
Enable integration of datasets in analysis platforms. Ensure integration with other RS products from various agencies (e.g. NASA). (D3.3)			DIAS, CEDS can be the vehicle, JRC Earth Observation Data and Processing Platform (JEODPP) could also have a role.	

Research

A2: Service evolution and expansion through Research and Development

Table 10 Non-priority actions under theme A2.

Action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects, actors etc)	Known bottlenecks
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Watershed modelling, hydrological and hydrodynamic modelling. Hydrological models to calculate hydrological fluxes for small streams or entire river basins in connection with sea. (WP1)	5	5		
Dedicated services for water level, altimetry, bathymetry (WP1)	7	6	e.g. IsardSAT	
A bathymetry product for water modelling (D5.2)	7	6		
Chlorophyll-a product with finer than 1 km spatial resolution for coastal waters (D5.2)	6	5	HR-OC	
Basin-scale high resolution surface models and topography data (WP1)	6-7	4-7		
Provide API to enable seamless use of real time or near real time data in models (D5.1)	6	5	FAIR projects.. ENVRI-FAIR,	
Transparency: provide technical reports on how processing is done and uncertainty bounds calculated. Improve findability, discoverability and referencing (e.g. DOI) (D5.1)	8	8	Variable level of detail provided in the Services	
Higher resolution soil moisture products for modelling e.g., daily at kilometre (D5.2)	6	6		
Provide products in Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) (D5.2)				
Spatial resolution of surface runoff and river discharge should be improved to less than 1km (D5.2)				
Spatial resolution of snowmelt products should be higher (<1000 m) (D5.2)	5	4	DEMs at 25m enable this	
Temporal resolution of groundwater products should be increased (<24 h) (D5.2)				User requirements need to be better defined
Evaporation and transpiration products at highest spatial resolution possible (D5.3, D3.3)	8	6		
High res regional products for water levels in lakes and rivers			SWOT mission	
Groundwater recharge - currently only available for greater Europe only, global coverage needed at hourly or daily frequencies				
DEM information at global (currently available for the EEA39 region only)				

A3: Innovation on multi-source, multi-scale observations and data integration

Table 11 Non-priority actions under theme A3.

Action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
A3.1: In situ observations				
Establish seamless links between the information from EO, drones, citizen science and in situ monitoring. (WP1)				
Satellite EO and in situ technologies like smart sensors, drones, IoT devices. can be developed to support the broader water sector. (WP1)				
Assess and improve the maturity of citizen science solutions and relevance of data outputs to contribute to ECVs and water products for management. (WP1)				
Support the development of UAV multispectral sensors designed for water quality variable estimates, compatible with optical configuration of current and future ocean colour sensors (D4.4)				
Establish standard protocols for UAV data acquisition. Develop guidelines for the collection of surface reflectance validation data by drones over inland and coastal waters covering different Optical Water Types (OWTs) (D4.4)				
Make use of the already developed low-cost sensor technology to create a network of sensors and community of practitioners (D4.4)	6	5	H2020 TWIGA and H2020 MONOCLE	
Intercomparison of (multiparameter) 'water quality probes' are needed to assess data quality and suitability for satellite cal-val (D4.4)				
Develop use of new autonomous sensors such as: DNA identification, flow-through absorption meters, and flow cytometers with optical characterisation capabilities (D2.2)				
A3.2: Space assets				
Implement and exploit additional optical wavebands in satellite sensors. (D2.2)				
Implement and exploit increased spatial resolution in satellite sensors (D2.2): Spatial resolution: from 5 up to 33 m. Spectral and radiometric resolutions: ideally hyperspectral, with contiguous bands from				

UV to NIR with an average band width of 5 nm (up to 8 nm) and possibly augmented by a SWIR imaging spectrometer. The radiometric resolution should be able to provide a NEΔL at ~ 0.005 mW m ⁻² sr ⁻¹ nm ⁻¹ (up to 0.010 mW m ⁻² sr ⁻¹ nm ⁻¹).				
Night-time observations (e.g., proposed GALENE) and geostationary satellites (e.g., GLIMR) will also support valuable applications and new services in an improved temporal domain.				
Glint avoidance: using tilt or roll for sun glint avoidance to increase the fraction of glint free acquisitions.				
A multi-mission/multi-sensor (MM/MS) to cover the variety of resolutions needed to observe aquatic ecosystems (see also D1.3) and to support improved and novel applications.				
<i>A3.3: Integration between in situ and remote observations</i>				
Perform inter-comparison exercises between UAV, ground data and satellite data to allow these data to be used for validation. (D4.4)				
Support research focused on synergistic approaches between UAV and satellite remote sensing: Multiscale Explanation, Model Calibration or Data fusion, to improve data interpretation and/or quality (D4.4)				
Explore appropriate use of big data analytics, AI, cloud computing etc. to inspect and assess the quality of datasets, integrate across spatiotemporal scales, and determine gaps.	3	2	R&D activities in digital twins context	

Coordination

Research

Innovation

Trust

[B] Management and hazards

Table 12 Non-priority actions within theme B.

Action	TRL	IRL	Current activities (projects etc)	Known bottlenecks
<i>Response coordination, assurance, early warning</i>				
Establish direct lines of communication between national and regional authorities and the European Flood Awareness System (WP3)	6	3		

Provide flood and drought risks at longer timescales relevant to the assurance and insurance sector (WP1)	5	5		
Dashboards or early warning systems for algal blooms and cyanobacteria (WP1)	6	6	Downstream (commercial) services	Few suitable satellite sensors, requiring additional wavebands (e.g. 620 nm).
<i>Pollution</i>				
Provide microbial, toxin, algal and metal indicators and plastic pollution indicators (WP1)	2	2		
<i>Systematic assessment</i>				
Assessment of current ability of Copernicus products to meet requirements of the Flood Directive and the Water Framework Directive (WP3)				
Develop water quality and water levels (quantity) of smaller reservoirs and rivers at catchment scale (WP1)	6	6		
Provide subsurface parameters observations (soil maps, groundwater etc.) (D3.2)	4	4		Lack of continuity in gravimetric missions
Expand land cover products: crops, vegetation type (D3.2)	7	8		Lack of time-series data
Expand drought products: temporary streams (D3.2)	3	1		Technical feasibility of resolving the spatial scale of streams
Expand flood products: Flood defence (D3.2)	6	3		Coordination; co-development of flood products, include regulators in process
Expand hydrology: River morphology, river discharge at appropriate resolution (D3.2)	4	4		Integration of RS, models and in situ observation
Expand soil products: groundwater flow, hydraulic properties/characteristics (D3.2)	4	4		
Expand water bodies products: morphology (D3.2)	6	6		

Coordination

Research

Innovation

[C] Management and environment, water accounting

Non-priority actions within theme C are shown below. TRL/IRL, ongoing activities and bottlenecks were not assessed for this list.

- Improve accessibility of open-source platforms for policy implementation (WP1 + others)
- Provide demonstrations of Copernicus data and services applied at local water management scales (D5.4)
- Provide demonstrations of Copernicus products merged with in situ networks (e.g. Finnish Tarkka system) (D5.4)
- Improve resolution of algal community structure and biomass (WP1)
- EO-based characterization, impact assessment and prediction of droughts (D3.3)
- Higher spatial resolution for surface water variables (such as surface runoff and river discharge or flood extent) used in predicting extent of floods (<1 km). (D5.2)
- Discrimination of permanent and temporary water bodies (WP1)
- Evapotranspiration processes (observations and forecasts) (WP1, D5.2)
- Continuous and consistent long-term archives of vegetation biophysical parameters coupled with land cover information (D5.2)
- Daily and high spatial resolution products; precipitation, soil moisture, evapotranspiration, surface runoff, inland water temperature, bathymetry, DEM and Water level (D5.2)
- Hourly flood extent, river discharge, and temperature (D5.2)
- Improved characterisation of state and dynamics of water bodies (D3.3)
- Improved Digital Elevation Models and Bathymetries for the coastal zone (D3.3)
- Improved monitoring and short- to long-term prediction of sea level in coastal zones (D3.3)
- Coastal and inland water skin temperature (WP1)
- Provide services dedicated to coastal areas. (WP1)
- Provide services focussed on shallow water (D2.2)
- Develop multi-source analytics for situational awareness in water management (WP1)
- Reduced latency of remotely sensed data for drought monitoring (D3.3)
- Effective drought monitoring with blended/fusion data from Landsat/Sentinel
- Nationally-approved and inter-calibrated hydrological assessment methods (D3.3)
- Set common QA/QC and data standards and reference datasets for water quantity products (D3.3)

Research

[D] Food and water security, climate resilience

Innovation

Non-priority actions within theme D are shown below. TRL/IRL, ongoing activities and bottlenecks were not assessed for this list.

Open water bodies

- Provide CDOM (coloured dissolved organic matter) and DOC (dissolved organic carbon) products to assist drinking water quality monitoring (WP1)
- Develop and validate products for shallow waters, primary production, microplastic, nutrients, other phytoplankton pigments, particular in areas used for water supply. (D2.2, D2.4)
- Nuisance algae in drinking water supplies (WP1)

Groundwater

- Couple groundwater level monitoring to land use change (WP1)

- Soil moisture/soil water balance (observations and forecasts), vertical moisture profiles in vegetation and soil (SMAP mission is a starting point) (WP1, D3.3, D5.2)

- Detection of soil salinization (WP1)

Water resource modelling

- Develop river cross-sections product for water resource modelling (D3.4)
- Develop hydraulic structures product for water resource modelling (D3.4)
- Develop reservoir geometry product for water resource modelling(D3.4)

Early warning

- Detect leakage from supply network (WP1)
- Forecast models and provision of early warning for food production and sustainable agriculture (WP1)

Land cover

- Microwave-based vegetation indices, for aboveground biomass and canopy density (D3.3).

Research

[E] Transport and recreation

Non-priority actions within theme E are shown below. TRL/IRL, ongoing activities and bottlenecks were not assessed for this list.

- Monitoring of fast-growing water plants and algae that could hinder vessel movement on inland waterways. (WP1)
- Risk-related indices to water systems: congestion, fishing jetties, flow speed, overgrowth, subsidence, sedimentation. (WP1)